

The Influence Of Education Level And Job Training Levels in The Performance Of State Civil Servent The Inspektorat Riau Province

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ARTICLE INFO :

ABSTRACT

Keywords :

Employee Performance,
Education Level,
Job Training,
Inpektorat Riau Province

This study was conducted at the Inspectorate of Riau Province with the objective of examining the influence of educational attainment and job training on employee performance at the regional Inspectorate of Riau Province. The sampling method employed was random sampling, with a total of 60 respondents. The R-squared value obtained from the data analysis is 0.544, indicating that the level of education and job training collectively account for 54% of the improvement in employee performance. The remaining 46% is influenced by factors not included in this study. The findings of this study demonstrate that education and job training are significant factors in enhancing employee performance in government agencies. However, it is important to recognise that there are other variables that also contribute to the overall performance of employees.

Article History :

Received :2024-07-16

Revised : 2024-08-10

Accepted :2024-09-29

Online :2024-09-30

INTRODUCTION

Accordance with the objectives of Human Resource Management (HRM), which include planning human resources up to the output process of competent human resources that can contribute to high productivity and performance. Utilizing quality and quantity of resource inputs, an efficient and effective organization will be produced.

The success of an organization does not only depend on how it develops human competencies, but also on how it supports the abilities of its employees in their work. The organization's support for the skills possessed by its employees is crucial, considering that the organizational environment, both internal and external, is constantly undergoing changes. The ability to work is absolutely essential for employees so that the activities or tasks they are responsible for can be completed well in accordance with the established guidelines.

Table 1. Employee Numbers Education Level at Regional Inspectorate of Riau Province

Numb.	Education Level	2022	2023	2024
1	Master (S2)	38	47	45
2	Graduate (S1)	89	87	87
3	Diploma	6	7	8
4	Senior High School	2	6	5
Total		135	147	145

Source: Inspectorate of Riau Province 2024

Over the three years, there was an increase in the number of employees with Master's and Diploma degrees, but a slight decrease in 2024. The number of employees with a Bachelor's degree is relatively stable. The number of employees with a high school education increases sharply in 2023, but decreases slightly in the following year. The total number of employees increased in 2023, but decreased slightly in 2024. In general, this table shows an increasing trend in the education of employees in this agency, with a dominance of employees with S1 and S2 education.

Table 2. Training for employees of the Regional Inspectorate of Riau Province

No.	Types of Training	Number of employees	The employees participate	Level
1	Bimtek dan ujian sertifikasi pengadaan barang dan jasa pada tahun 2021	135	5	Golongan 3 (Online)
2	Diklat penjenjangan fungsional P2UPD jenjang madya tahun 2021 (PNPB)	135	3	Golongan 4 (Online)
3	Diklat pembentukan jabatan fungsional pengawas penyelenggaraan urusan Pemerintah di Daerah (P2UPD) tahun 2021	135	5	Golongan 3 dan 4 (Offline)
4	Diklat pembentukan jabatan fungsional pengawas penyelenggaraan urusan Pemerintah di Daerah (P2UPD) tahun 2021	135	6	Golongan 3 (Offline)
5	Diklat Training Of Trainers pengawasan penyelenggaraan urusan Pemerintah di Daerah (P2UPD) tahun 2021	135	1	Golongan 4 (Online)
6	Pelatihan Audit bagi Aparatur pengawasan tahun 2021 di lingkungan Inspektorat Daerah Provinsi Riau	135	80	Golongan 3 dan 4 (Offline)
7	Diklat pembentukan jabatan fungsional pengawas penyelenggaraan urusan Pemerintah di Daerah (P2UPD) Tahun 2021	135	5	Golongan 3 (Online)
8	Pelatihan pengembangan tenaga pemeriksa dan Aparatur Pengawasan tahun 2021 di lingkungan Inspektorat Daerah Provinsi Riau	135	97	Golongan 3 dan 4 (Offline)
9	Diklat fungsional dan uji kompetensi pengawas pemerintah jenjang Muda Angkatan III tahun 2022	147	2	Golongan 3 (Offline)
10	Diklat pembentukan P2UPD jenjang Madya tahun 2022	147	5	Golongan 4 (Offline)
11	Diklat penjenjangan Auditor Muda secara tatap muka (blended)	147	3	Golongan 3

	learning) tahun 2022			(Offline)
12	Diklat penjenjangan Auditor Muda secara tatap muka (blended learning) tahun 2022	147	1	Golongan 3 (Offline)
13	Diklat penjenjangan Auditor Madya dengan metode tatap muka jarak jauh tahun 2022	147	1	Golongan 4 (Online)

Source: Inspectorate of Riau Province, 2024

Table 3. Average Performance of Employees of the Regional Inspectorate of Riau Province

No	Years	Criteria Assesment		Work Performance Assessment	Category
		Average Score	Work Behavior		
1	2021	90,0	80,3	87,8	Good
2	2022	91,6	80,8	90,5	Good
3	2023	91,3	90,2	91,8	Good

Source: Inspectorate of Riau Province, 2024

In the effort to implement activities to achieve the targets set by the Regional Inspectorate of Riau Province, several obstacles and challenges have been encountered, namely:

1. The civil servants who understand their duties and functions as employees, particularly regarding the understanding of inspections.
2. The work discipline of employees is still low, evidenced by the fact that some employees arrive late and leave early.
3. The training conducted has not been focused on supporting the enhancement of work capabilities, as it is evident that some participants do not take the training seriously.
4. The number of training participants is decreasing.

LITERATURE REVIEW AND HYPOTHESIS DEVELOPMENT

A. Employee Performance

A company can be said to be successful if its human resource performance strives to enhance employee performance in order to achieve the established goals of the company. According to Sandy (2015:11), performance is an achievement that has been attained by employees in carrying out the tasks assigned to them. According to Sutrisno (2016:151), performance or work achievement is the result of work that has been accomplished by an individual based on their work behavior while carrying out their job activities.

Based on the above understanding, it can be concluded that employee performance is the achievement of results by employees in the process of carrying out their tasks in accordance with the responsibilities assigned. Improving employee performance, it will have a positive impact on the company, ensuring that employees have a good and optimal level of performance to help realize the company's goals.

B. Performance Assessment

According to Rivai (2014:406), Performance Assessment is a formal and structured system used to measure, evaluate, and influence characteristics related to work, behavior, and outcomes, including the level of absenteeism.

According to Bintoro (2017:194), performance appraisal is a process that allows an organization to know, evaluate, measure, and assess the performance of its members accurately and precisely. This activity is closely related to and influences the effectiveness of human resource activities within the company, such as promotions, compensation, training, career development, and others. This is because the performance evaluation function can provide important information to the company to improve decision-making and offer feedback to employees about their actual performance.

C. Factors Influencing Education

According to Hasbullah (2014:63), the factors influencing education are as follows:

1. Ideology All humans are born with equal rights, especially the right to receive education and knowledge.
2. Socioeconomic A higher socioeconomic status enables a person to attain a higher level of education.
3. Socio-Cultural Many parents are still unaware of the importance of formal education for their children.
4. 4.The Development of Science and Technology The development of science and technology requires constant updating of knowledge.
5. Psychology The conceptual framework of education serves as a tool to enhance individual personality for the better.

D. Training

Training prepares participants to take specific courses of action outlined by the technology and organization they work for, and helps them improve their performance in their activities, particularly regarding understanding and skills. The definition of training according to experts is as follows:

According to Mangkunegara (2016:44), training is a short-term educational process that uses systematic and organized procedures in which non-managerial employees learn knowledge and technical skills for specific purposes. According to Sutrisno (2016:67), training is an effort to improve the work performance (performance) of employees in their current job or in another job they will soon hold.

According to Dessler (2015:284), training is the process of teaching new or existing employees the basic skills they need to perform their jobs. Training is one of the efforts to improve the quality of human resources in the workforce.

Both new and existing employees need to undergo training. Based on the opinions of the experts above, it can be said that training is a tool for human resource management used to acquire the skills, abilities, or attitudes of employees in order to enhance their work performance.

E. Previous Research

Table 4. Previous Research

No	Author Name	Heading	Result
1.	Fitta Kurniasari (2014)	"The Influence of Training on Employee Performance at the Purwosari Subdistrict Office"	Regarding the positive and significant influence of training on employee performance at the Purwosari sub-district office. Regarding the positive and significant influence of training on employee performance at the Purwosari sub-district office.
2.	Juliana (2015)	"The Influence of Education Level on Employee Performance at the Regional Development Planning Agency of Enrekang	There is a positive and significant influence of education level on employee performance at the Regional Development Planning Agency

		Regency"	of Enrekang Regency. There is a positive and significant influence of education level on employee performance at the Regional Development Planning Agency of Enrekang Regency.
3	Emi Hayati, Syofia Achnes, Andi M Rifiyan , 2018	"The Influence of Education and Training on Employee Performance at the Regional Library and Archives Office of Special Region of Yogyakarta"	There is a positive and significant influence of education on employee performance at the Regional Library and Archives Office of Special Region of Yogyakarta. There is a positive and significant influence of training on employee performance at the Regional Library and Archives Office of Special Region of Yogyakarta. There is a positive and significant influence of education and training on employee performance at the Regional Library and Archives Agency of the Special Region of Yogyakarta.

METHODS

The population is a generalized area consisting of objects or subjects that have certain quantities and characteristics determined by the researcher for study and subsequent conclusions. In this research, the population is all employees in the Regional Inspectorate of Riau Province 145. So the sample obtained in this study is 59.18 or 60 people with an error tolerance of 0.1. The sampling was conducted using random sampling, meaning that each member of the population has an equal chance and opportunity to be selected as a sample, with no specific intervention from the researcher.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION**1. Data Quality Test****a. Validity Test****Table 5. Validity Result Test**

Quest	Corrected item-total correlation	Mark	r Table	Inf.
Employee Performance (Y)				
Y.1	0,637	>	0,1764	Valid
Y.2	0,517	>	0,1764	Valid
Y.3	0,510	>	0,1764	Valid
Y.4	0,548	>	0,1764	Valid
Y.5	0,459	>	0,1764	Valid
Education Level (X₁)				
X1.1	Y.9	>	0,1764	Valid
X1.2	0,568	>	0,1764	Valid
Job Training (X₂)				
X2.1	0,603	>	0,1764	Valid
X2.2	0,584	>	0,1764	Valid
X2.3	0,615	>	0,1764	Valid
X2.4	0,589	>	0,1764	Valid
X2.5	0,672	>	0,1764	Valid

Source : SPSS Data Processed , 2024

Based on the table above, it is evident that each statement item for the dependent and independent variables exceeds the criterion of 0.1764 (r table). Therefore, it can be concluded that statistically, each statement indicator for the dependent and independent variables is valid and suitable for use as research data.

b. Reability Result Test**Table 6. Reliability Result Test**

Variabel	Cronbach's Alpha	Mark	Result	Conclusion
Employee Performance (Y)	0,770	>	0,60	Reliabel
Education Level (X ₁)	0.722	>	0,60	Reliabel
Job Training (X ₂)	0,782	>	0,60	Reliabel

Source : SPSS Data Processed , 2024

Based on the table above, it is known that the Cronbach's alpha values for all variables are greater than 0.60, so it can be concluded that all instruments in this study are reliable and suitable for test.

c. Multikolinieritas Test

Table 7. Multikolinierity Test

Coefficients ^a			
Model		Collinearity Statistics	
		Tolerance	VIF
1	Education Level (X1)	.690	1.449
	Job Training (X2)	.690	1.449

a. Dependent Variable: Employee Performance (Y)

Source : SPSS Data Processed , 2024

The table above, it can be seen that each independent variable has a tolerance value > 0.10 and a VIF value < 10. Therefore, referring to the decision-making criteria in the multicollinearity test, it can be concluded that there is no multicollinearity in this regression model.

d. Autocorellation Result Test

Table 8. Autocorellation Result Test

Model Summary ^b					
Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate	Durbin-Watson
1	.738 ^a	.544	.537	2.304	1.704

a. Predictors: (Constant), Job Training (X2), Education Level (X1)
b. Dependent Variable: Employee Performance (Y)

Source : SPSS Data Processed , 2024

e. Multiple Regression Analysis

Table 9. Multiple Regression Analysis

Coefficients ^a						
Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	T	Sig.
		B	Std. Error	Beta		
1	(Constant)	5.801	3.040		1.909	.059
	Educational Level (X1)	.526	.078	.498	6.742	.000
	Job Training (X2)	.333	.074	.334	4.520	.000

a. Dependent Variable: Employee Performance (Y)

Source : SPSS Data Processed , 2024

The regression equation, there are:

- 1) Constant value (α) of 5.801. This means that if the level of education (X1) and training (X2) are assumed to be zero (0), then performance (Y) remains at 5.801.
- 2) Regression coefficient value of 0.526 indicates that for every 1 unit increase in the level of education (X1), the performance variable (Y) will increase by 0.526.
- 3) Regression coefficient value of 0.333 indicates that for every 1 unit increase in training (X2), the performance variable (Y) will increase by 0.333. The standard error (e) is a random variable and has a probability distribution that represents all factors influencing Y but are not included in the equation.

f. Hipotesis Test

Table 10. Hipotesis Test (t result)

Coefficients ^a						
Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	T	Sig.
		B	Std. Error	Beta		
1	(Constant)	5.801	3.040		1.909	.059
	Education Level (X1)	.526	.078	.498	6.742	.000
	Job Training (X2)	.333	.074	.334	4.520	.000

a. Dependent Variable: Employee Performance (Y)

Source : SPSS Data Processed , 2024

Based on the table above, the results of the hypothesis testing partially (T) will be discussed as follows:

- 1) The education level variable shows a positive and significant effect on performance, with a calculated t value of 6.742 > t table of 1.979 and a significance level (0.000) < 0.05. This means that, in isolation, the education level variable has an impact on performance.
- 2) The training variable also shows a positive and significant effect on performance, with a calculated t value of 4.520 > t table of 1.979 and a significance level (0.000) < 0.05. This indicates that, in isolation, the training variable affects performance.

Table 11. Simultan Result Test (f result)

ANOVA ^a						
Model		Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	767.700	2	383.850	72.316	.000 ^b
	Residual	642.259	121	5.308		
	Total	1409.960	123			

a. Dependent Variable: Employee Performance (Y)

b. Predictors: (Constant), Job Training (X2), Education Level (X1)

Source : SPSS Data Processed , 2024

Based on the table above, it can be seen that the calculated F value is 72.316 > the table f value of 3.07 with a significance value of 0.000 < 0.05. This means that simultaneously, the variables of education level and training have a positive impact on the performance of the Riau provincial inspectorate.

g. Determination Coefficient Result Test

Table 12. Determination Coefficient Result Test

Model Summary ^b					
Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate	Durbin-Watson
1	.738 ^a	.544	.537	2.304	1.704

a. Predictors: (Constant), Education Level (X2), Job Training (X1)

b. Dependent Variable: Employee Performance (Y)

Source : SPSS Data Processed , 2024

Based on the table above, it can be seen that the correlation value (R) obtained is 0.738. Therefore, it can be concluded that there is a strong correlation between the level of education and training and performance. Meanwhile, the R Square value is 0.544. This indicates that the variable of education level and job training has an influence of 54% on performance, while the remaining 46% is influenced by other variables not examined in this study.

The Influence Of Education Level On Performance

The t-test on education level (X1) yielded a calculated t value of 6.742 > t table 1.979 and sig (0.000) < 0.05. This indicates that the education level variable (X1) has a positive and significant effect on performance in a partial manner. The hypothesis states that "the level of education has an impact on the performance of employees in the Riau Provincial Inspectorate, accepted."

The Influence Of Training On Performance

The t-test for training (X2) yielded a calculated t value of 4.520, which is greater than the table t value of 1.979, and a significance level (0.000) that is less than 0.05. This indicates that the training variable (X2) has a positive and significant effect on performance in a partial manner. The hypothesis states that "training has an impact on the performance of employees in the Riau Provincial Inspectorate, accepted."

The Influence Of Education Level And Job Training On Performance

The hypothesis simultaneously regarding the influence of independent variables on the dependent variable, an F-test was used. Through the F-test, a significant simultaneous effect was found from all the independent variables used, including education level and training on performance. It can be seen that the calculated F value is 72.316 > the table F value of 3.07 with a significance value of 0.000 < 0.05. This means that the levels of education and training jointly influence the performance of employees in the Riau Provincial Inspectorate. Based on the explanation above, it can be concluded that both the levels of education and training have a simultaneous effect on performance.

CONCLUSION

The results of the research that has been conducted, the conclusions that can be drawn from this study are:

- 1) The level of education has a positive and significant effect on the performance of employees in the Inspectorate of Riau Province. With the education level variable value, it is known that the level of education has a positive and significant influence on performance with a calculated t value of 6.742 > t table 1.979 and sig (0.000) < 0.05. This means that, partially, the education level variable affects performance.
- 2) The Training has a positive and significant effect on the performance of employees in the Inspectorate of Riau Province. With the training variable value, it is known that training has a positive and significant influence on performance with a calculated t value of 4.520 > t table 1.979 and sig (0.000) < 0.05. This means that, partially, the training variable affects performance. Inspectorate employees in Riau Province
- 3) The level of education and training has an impact on the performance of the Provincial Inspectorate employees in Riau. With an F calculated value of 72.316 > F table value of 3.07 and a significance value of 0.000 < 0.05. This means that, simultaneously, the variables of education level and training collectively influence the performance of the Inspectorate employees in Riau Province.

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